

Mechanistic aspects of the selectivity of RuO₂ and Ru-Mn-O catalysts in parallel Chlorine and Oxygen Evolutions Reactions

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Abstract: Mechanistic differences between oxygen evolution and chlorine evolution on Ru based oxide electrodes in acid media were assessed by operando soft X-ray absorption spectroscopy. O K edge spectra recorded under cyclic polarization in 0.1 M HClO₄ containing variable concentrations of chlorides in energy dispersion mode were used to follow a potential dependence of the key intermediates of the oxygen evolution process as a function of the electrode potential and chloride concentration. In the absence of chlorides, the OER process is characterized by a formation of surface confined OOH at potentials preceding the onset of the bulk oxygen evolution. In the presence of chlorides, the spectral behavior reflects a change of the electrode selectivity towards chlorine evolution as shows a suppression of the absorption of the gaseous oxygen as well as intermediates of OER process. The observed behavior is compliant with the mechanism assuming the chlorine binding via surface confined oxygen atoms. The Ru-Mn-O phases which are selective for oxygen evolution even in the presence of chlorides show a different behavior. The sites involved in the OER retain their selectivity to OER even in the presence of chlorides. The actual mechanism of the OER changes in the presence of chlorides. While in the absence of chlorides, one observes accumulation of surface OOH groups only at potentials positive to the onset of the bulk oxygen evolution, the presence of chlorides enables the formation of surface confined OOH at potentials negative to the OER onset. The onset of the actual oxygen evolution, on the other hand, leads to removal of the surface confined OOH suggesting the OER is controlled by the third electron transfer in the presence of chlorides.

Introduction:

Hydrogen production for renewable energy storage has increased interest in electrocatalytic gas evolving reactions as the water electrolysis represents the most promising process for environmentally acceptable production of hydrogen. In fact, water electrolysis as a process is not actually controlled by cathodic hydrogen evolution but kinetically sluggish oxygen evolution which represents the main limiting factor for a large scale deployment of water electrolyzers [1]. It also needs to be added that the large-scale utilization of electrolytic hydrogen generation can face a problem with availability and purity of fresh water for water electrolysis namely due to need to avoid a presence of chlorides. An alternative solution represents a desalination of sea water or ultimately a sea water electrolysis [2-5,] in which one needs to tackle a parallel anodic chlorine evolution.

Anodically generated chlorine represents an unwanted byproduct of the electrolysis of chloride containing water due to its toxicity and corrosiveness. A selectivity control of the parallel anodic gas evolution reactions represents a fundamental issue which can be addressed either via exploring a different pH dependence of both processes [4,6] and/or by controlling the intrinsic selectivity of the catalysts surface [7]. As a result of a different pH dependence of chlorine and oxygen evolution one may increase the thermodynamic preference of OER (at a constant potential) which increases with increasing pH. An alternative approach towards selectivity control can be associated with engineering the surface to control nature and abundance of the active sites supporting corresponding electrode reactions [5, 8-11] to steer the selectivity of the oxide catalyst surface in these gas evolving reactions. One needs to stress the fact that a detailed understanding of both electrode processes and their mechanisms is prerequisite to rational design of novel selective electrode materials [12].

Despite the undisputable success of experiments to prepare novel catalytically active systems with controlled selectivity [5, 9-11, 15-16] there are practically no experimental reports which would pin down the actual mechanism of both gas evolving reactions at electrode surfaces. The anodic gas evolving on oxide-based surfaces has been treated theoretically [8, 17-20]. This theoretical analysis was based on practical application of Bronsted-Polanyi relations which allow to assess thermodynamic limits of kinetic behavior by comparing the driving forces of given reactions at different electrode surfaces. Such DFT based thermodynamic analysis clearly points towards a kinetic preference of chlorine evolution for most of the conceivable surfaces [8]. The chlorine as well as oxygen evolution in relevant pH range proceed under rather harsh conditions which explains a disproportionate attention paid to the behavior of electrode materials based on noble metal oxides (mostly on Ru and Ir) and their solid solutions with, e.g. Ti [21-25].

Regarding the practical steering of the selectivity in parallel oxygen and chlorine evolution it was shown that preference for a particular gas evolving reaction can be altered by controlling surface stress and strain of the catalytically active layer [21, 26]. The selectivity of the Ru based catalysts is also affected by chemical composition and/or by the local structure as has been shown for ternary systems like of the Ru-Me-O (Me = Ni, Mn, Zn, Mg) type [5, 9-11]. A similar local structure effect has been also reported for well-defined single-phase catalysts in Ru-Ti-O system [27]. In a similar manner, the behavior of Ir based systems, despite less favorable cost, was in detail treated for Ir based double perovskites [28] or for phases in Ir-Mn-O system [12]. It needs to be noted that the results of these studies still have to be corroborated theoretically. In the light of the prospective use of novel catalysts in hydrogen producing electrolysis of chloride containing solutions one needs to pay particular attention to the several systems

which have been reported to steer the selectivity of the surface towards oxygen evolution even in presence of significant chloride content [5, 12-16]. Using the ruthenium-based oxides related to DSA as model materials one needs to stress that a substitution with Zn [5] or Mn [12,16] yields materials with a particular tendency to evolve the oxygen from chloride containing media. In this light these systems significantly differ from those substituted by Ni [11] or Mg [9] which show a high preference for chlorine evolution.

The generalized computational models of the oxygen and chlorine evolution on Ru oxide-based surfaces predict a competition of both electrode reactions for the surface-active sites for all involved surfaces. The proposed active site competition has, however, never been proved experimentally. [6] The lack of experimental evidence regarding the nature of the active sites and/or of the reaction mechanism can be in part connected with the experimental difficulty to address the actual surface structure under operando conditions of oxygen and/or of chlorine evolution. This situation has changed recently with the advent of the operando soft X-ray spectroscopic techniques [29-30]. While the hard- X-ray based spectroscopic techniques have been explored for several decades due to their compatibility with the conditions of the anodic gas evolving reactions, their actual impact on the understanding of these processes was rather limited by bulk nature of X-ray absorption spectroscopy. The use of soft X-rays in part removes the of limited surface sensitivity since the fluoresce registered in soft X-ray absorption spectroscopy originates in relatively thin surface layer thickness of which does not exceed hundreds of nanometers. In fact the operando soft X-ray exploring techniques (both XPS [29] and XAS [30-31]) have been employed to address the behavior of some Ru and Ir based catalysts in oxygen evolution reaction.

Given the interdependence of both anodic gas evolving reactions at oxide base electrode surfaces one may use O K edge soft XAS to characterize the selectivity control of the anode surface in parallel OER and CER reactions. The oxygen evolution reaction is conventionally described as a sequence of four consecutive one electron one proton steps as outlined in sequence of reactions (1)-(4):

Aside of the DFT based investigations, the OER reaction mechanism has been also followed up experimentally using the soft X-rays based techniques, which proved to be instrumental in following the surface population of theoretically conceived reaction intermediates – namely those formed in the reactions (1) and (2) [29-34]. Aside of the qualitative and quantitative determination of the surface confined oxygen containing species acting as OER intermediates, the soft X-ray absorption spectroscopy reflects the development of the local electronic structure near the transition metal. The energy dispersive operando O K edge XAS data clearly show that the bulk oxygen evolution leads to a change in the local electronic structure under OER conditions. This change in the electronic structure shows itself in suppression probability of the excitation of the O 1s electrons into antibonding bands formed by a hybridization of O 2p* orbitals with Ru 3d e_g orbitals [33].

The chlorine evolution process, on the other hand includes a transfer of only two electrons and can be summarized by two conceivable reaction sequences [6] summarized by equations (5)-(7) and (8)-(9)

It needs to be noted that while the reaction sequence (5)-(7) represents a catalytic cycle formally independent of the possible oxygen evolution process which may proceed simultaneously. The reaction sequence represented by processes (8)-(9) relies on the same active sites as the catalytic cycle of the OER and suggests strong competition between both electrode processes. At the same time, it clearly identifies the O K edge XAS as a convenient tool to follow the actual drivers controlling the selectivity of the oxide surfaces in parallel oxygen and chlorine evolution.

This paper extends the previous studies when the O K edge X-ray absorption spectroscopy was employed to follow the oxygen evolution process on Ru oxide based surfaces. We compare the data obtained by energy dispersed XAS to elucidate the chemical changes

governing the selectivity behavior of the Ru based oxides. Specifically we compare here a behavior of pure RuO₂, which is known to be rather selective for CER, with that of Ru_{0.95}Mn_{0.05}O₂ which has been reported to retain high oxygen evolving selectivity [12-16] even in presence of significant chloride concentrations.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 XAS Experiments

The soft X-ray absorption spectroscopy of nanoparticulate Ru and Ru-Mn oxides were measured on BL-16A of the Photon Factory under high vacuum conditions. The XAS spectra were measured in conventional stepwise manner in the energy range 510 – 670 eV. The individual step size was 1 eV scan with integration time of 3 s. The absorption spectrum was recorded in partial fluorescence mode with single element silicon drift detector (SDD) (SGX Sensortech) used as fluorescence detector.

Real-time *in-situ* XAS measurements on O K-edge were performed in total fluorescence-yield mode using wavelength-dispersive XAS approach [35]. All the experiments were performed at the beamline BL-16A of the Photon Factory of the High Energy Accelerator Research Organization (KEK), Japan [35]. Figure 1 shows the schematic image of the apparatus configuration. The electrochemical cell filled with liquid electrolyte solution (0.1M HClO₄) was separated from the high vacuum part of the XAS apparatus (beamline and imaging optics) by a Si₃N₄ window (NTT-AT Japan), which was fabricated on a Si wafer with a thickness of 200 nm and dimensions of 1 mm × 3 mm.

The spatial dispersion of the synchrotron radiation at exit slit of the soft X-ray monochromator [30] was achieved with a 500-lines/mm diffraction grating optimized to provide soft X-rays around the O K-edge (approximately 530 eV). Incoming X-rays on the

grating are diffracted according to their wavelength at distinctive angles and as a result of it, individual wavelengths hit different positions at the sample. The fluorescence signals proportional to the absorption of incident soft X-rays were recorded simultaneously using metal oxide semiconductor (CMOS) camera (Marana-X, Andor) used as a detector (pixel size and detection area were $6.5 \mu\text{m} \times 6.5 \mu\text{m}$ and $13 \text{mm} \times 13 \text{mm}$, respectively). The spatial separation of the fluorescence X-ray signals was ensured by two spherical mirrors (see Figure 1). The intensity readings from each pixel of the CMOS camera were converted into absorption coefficient at individual energy. To compensate for energy dependence of incident X-ray intensity and position dependence of the detection efficiency, the measured fluorescence signals were normalized by those of CaF_2 representing I_0 . The collected O K-edge spectra were recorded in the range 525-535 eV with time-resolution of ca. 3 s per spectrum.

2.2 Electrochemical cell set-up

The electrochemical part of the experiments was realized in a three electrode PTFE single compartment cell with Pt auxiliary electrode and Ag/AgCl reference electrode [33]. All potentials were then recalculated and are quoted in reversible hydrogen scale (RHE). The PTFE cell was equipped with a Si_3N_4 window to provide a connection to high-vacuum part of the beamline. The working electrodes composed of RuO_2 and $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ were deposited directly on Si_3N_4 window. The RuO_2 electrode was initially prepared by Ru deposition by electron beam evaporation (E-flux, ADCAP Vacuum Technology Co., Ltd.). The thickness of the deposited Ru was 20 nm (with 10 nm of sputtered Ti underlayer on Si_3N_4 window before depositing Ru). RuO_2 electrode was prepared by a thermal oxidation of deposited Ru layer at 600°C for 1 hour. The thickness of the deposited layers and underlayers was optimized to

achieve less than 60% of the attenuation of the X-rays in the electrode and interphase to enable a detection of the generated fluorescence from the backside through the window.

In the case of the $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ the original nanoparticulate catalysts (particle size 10 nm) was prepared by spray freeze freeze drying approach as described in [12]. Final electrodes for XAS measurements were prepared by a drop casting from an ink containing Ru-Mn-O directly on the Ti covered Si_3N_4 window. The Ru-Mn-O containing ink was prepared from water-based suspension containing 2 g of the prepared Ru-Mn-O materials per liter of suspension. The necessary film stability was achieved by an addition of 15 μL of Nafion suspension. The suspension was freshly sonicated before deposition of 20 μL of the ink at the Si_3N_4 window. The deposited films were X-ray transparent at energies close to 530 eV and sufficiently homogeneous with respect to lateral resolution of the fluorescence detector.

The deposited electrodes were contacted by an indium solder. The solder and contacting lead were insulated by non-conductive epoxy resin. The potential control during the experiments was operated by an HSV-110 automatic polarization system (Hokuto Denko, Japan). All experiments were performed in 0.1 M HClO_4 (pH=1) which was de-aerated prior and during experiments.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Ruthenium dioxide

A comparison of electrochemical behavior of RuO_2 electrode in acidic solution in chloride free and chloride containing solutions is given in Figure 2. Despite the similarity of current responses of RuO_2 electrode to a cyclic polarization in chloride free (see Figure 2a) and chloride containing (see Figure 2b) perchloric acid (pH=1), a closer examination shows a

profound effect of the presence of chlorides on the electrocatalytic activity of ruthenium dioxide in anodic gas evolving reactions. Addition of chlorides to an overall chloride concentration 0.05M leads to two notable changes in the observed voltammograms. In presence of chlorides one observes a significant increase of the anodic activity of the RuO₂ electrode. This overall increase in the electrocatalytic activity is also accompanied with a decrease of the onset of the exponential current increase by about 50 mV to less positive potentials. It needs to be noted that in both cases the shape of the recorded voltammograms is affected by relatively high uncompensated iR drop associated with low thickness of the metal contact at the Si₃N₄ window (10 nm) which, namely in the case of chloride free solutions, dominates the double layer charging current driving both branches of the voltammogram to anodic values. The contribution of the double layer charging gets more pronounced in chloride containing solutions which suggests an enhanced corrosion of RuO₂ electrodes in chloride containing media.

It needs to be noted that the recorded anodic current in the case of chloride free solution – in the potential interval characterized by exponential current response can be attributed to the oxygen evolution, the current response in chloride containing solution is composed of two contributions corresponding aside of OER also to chlorine evolution (CER). It is also known [19] that ruthenium oxides show a high selectivity towards chlorine evolution hence one should expect a profound effect of the chloride presence on the operando O K edge spectra.

A summary of the spectro-electrochemical behavior of RuO₂ in chloride free and chloride containing solutions is shown in Figure 3 which presents two- dimensional contour maps reflecting the changes of XAS peak intensities recorded during cyclic polarization. The anodic

behavior in chloride free media has been reported previously and it is characterized by a pronounced increase in absorption at 531 eV upon anodic polarization [33].

This increase in absorption integrates two main contributions – one attributable to the surface confined OOH groups [31] and to the electrochemically evolved gaseous oxygen [37] (see Figure 4a). The main increase in the population of oxygen containing reaction intermediates which coincides with the exponential increase of the anodic current is accompanied with a pronounced reversible decrease of the absorption at 533 eV (see Figure 4c) which is attributed to a change in local electronic structure triggered by the start of the catalytic cycle of the oxygen evolution. The onset of the bulk oxygen evolution significantly affects the population of electronic states available to accommodate excited 1s electrons of oxygen [33, 36].

In presence of chlorides, one observes significantly altered spectral response. In contrast to the chloride free solutions the main area of spectral response is observed in the spectral region 532-533 eV. A detailed outline of the specific changes to O K edge absorption in the energy range relevant to OER triggered by chloride presence is given in Figures 4a-d. It also needs to be stressed that the XAS spectra recorded in absence of chlorides are essentially independent of the electrode history, the K O edge spectra recorded in the same potential range in presence of chlorides show pronounced development during electrode cycling. The most notable change with respect to the behavior recorded in absence of chlorides one encounters at the energy of 531 eV (see Figure 4a). In the case of the experiments carried out in absence of chlorides the absorption coefficient at this energy reversibly increases with electrode potential to reflect an accumulation of surface confined OOH groups [31, 33] as well electrocatalytic formation of oxygen. The same experiment carried out in chloride containing solution shows strikingly different behavior in which the absorbance at 531 eV on pristine

electrode initially increases with applied potential to reflect formation of oxygen as well as its intermediates at the surface. In contrast to chloride free solutions, however, the increase in absorbance changes into a plateau at potentials positive to 1.7 V vs RHE. This behavior suggests a blocking of the surface via chloride adsorption at these potentials as the absorption coefficient at 531 eV (reflecting the population of O₂ as well as OOH) show little sensitivity to the applied potential. Further cycling of the electrode in the whole potential range causes no change of the absorption at 531 eV (see red and blue curves in Figure 4a). This type of behavior indicates that the anodic polarization of the RuO₂ in presence of 0.05M of chlorides leads to little formation of oxygen.

Surprisingly, there is practically no difference in spectral response recorded at 529 eV in presence and absence of chlorides (see Fig. 4b). The observed behavior indicates that a formation of OH /O species at the surface is not perturbed by the presence of chloride and is not directly related to catalytic cycle of oxygen evolution nor of chlorine evolution. Coincidentally, one observes a dramatic change of the potential controlled absorption at 533 eV (see Figure 4c). The change in absorption at 533 eV in absence of chlorides (when the electrode exclusively evolves oxygen) is attributed to a change in the local electronic structure of the catalyst under operando conditions connect with the flow of the electrons removed from water into the external circuit. [33] The reversible decrease of the absorption at 533 eV is proportional to the extent of the OER. In presence of chlorides the RuO₂ surface may in principle support two anodic reactions - oxygen evolution and chlorine evolution with the later one being kinetically preferred resulting in high selectivity of the RuO₂ surface towards chlorine evolution [reference]. This shift in selectivity towards CER apparently disturbs the electron transfer connected with OER resulting in potential controlled increase of the absorption at 533 eV in OER/CER relevant potential range (see Figure 4c).

Aside of the absorption changes reflecting the formation of the oxygen containing intermediates as well as of the formed oxygen one also observes a change of the absorption in the energy range characteristic for liquid water. While in the case of the regime when the RuO₂ supports only oxygen evolution one observes a hysteretic decrease of the absorption at 534 eV (see Figure 4d) at potentials positive to 1.7 V vs RHE, in the case of chloride containing solutions one observes slightly different behavior when the absorption at 534 eV decreases at potential positive to 1.2 V and remains potential independent at potentials positive to 1.4 V. It needs to be stressed that the spectral change at 534 eV is fully reversible showing no hysteresis between anodic and cathodic branches of the voltammogram. The observed behavior is compliant with a situation when the total water content in the double layer decreases with potential. Such a behavior can be expected reflecting the fact that anodic both oxygen as well as chlorine evolution require a polarization positive to E_{pzc} leading to a population of the double layer with anions. In our particular case we should reflect the fact that the system contains two types of anions – perchlorates (which dominate the double layer and are redox inactive) and chlorides which represent a minority anions and which are consumed in the chlorine evolution. The observed decrease of the water absorbance then can be ascribed to a difference in the solvation of both present anions – chlorides and perchlorates where the former is more solvated (binding approximately 6 molecules of water per anion) while the perchlorate is comparably less solvated averaging just 3 molecules of water per anion [30]. It may be therefore assumed, that the chloride consumption via chlorine evolution inevitably leads to an increase of the perchlorate population in the double layer resulting in a overall decrease of the water content in the double layer. The absence of hysteresis between anodic and cathodic branches observed in presence of chlorides can be taken as an additional confirmation of the chlorine evolution dominance. It is worth noting that in absence of

chlorides (when oxygen evolution dominates the electrode process), one encounters a complex response of the absorption at 534 eV corresponding to water population near the electrode. The potential triggered absorption change at this energy is rather small and difficult to rationalize.

3.2 Ru-Mn-O based catalysts

While ruthenium dioxide may serve as a model catalyst selective to chlorine evolution in chloride containing media ruthenium-based oxides substituted with Mn have been reported to retain high selectivity towards oxygen evolution even in presence of chlorides [12, 16]. Interestingly the O K edge absorption spectrum of the Ru-Mn-O catalysts regardless of the actual Mn content does not differ significantly from that reported for RuO₂[36] (see Figure 5). The O K edge absorption spectrum is dominated by two signals located at 529.6 and 532.5 eV, respectively. These two signals are typical for excitation of the 1s electron of oxygen into bands formed by a hybridization of the antibonding O 2p orbitals with t_{2g} and e_g 3d orbitals of Ru. In this light, the intensity of the absorption at 529.6 and 532.5 eV reflects the distribution of the vacant electronic states in the material. A minimal difference between the absorption behavior of the RuO₂ and that of the Ru-Mn-O oxides indicates that the present Mn has apparently negligible effect on the electronic structure of the prepared materials which remains controlled by ruthenium. At the same time one may note a presence of two more absorption signals appearing at 539.5 and 543 eV which can be attributed to water adsorbed at the surface. It needs to be noted that the strength of this surface related signal seems to be affected by chemical composition suggesting that incorporation of Mn increases hydrophobicity of the prepared catalysts.

The preference of Ru-Mn-O surfaces towards oxygen evolution is reflected also in the O K edge X-ray absorption spectra measured under operando conditions. In contrast to ruthenium dioxide, the overall electrocatalytic activity is not significantly affected by the presence of chlorides (see Figure 6). Regardless of the chloride presence or its concentration, the Ru-Mn-O catalysts show an exponential current increase in voltammograms when the electrode potential exceeds 1.5 V vs RHE. This exponential current increase is preceded by a poorly pronounced double layer region characterized by small charging current in the potential range between 1.0 and 1.5 V. It needs to be noted that the capacitive current remains rather low and decreases with increasing chloride concentration. The overall current response in the double layer region remains dominated by an uncompensated iR drop due to a thin layer nature of the current collector (10 nm of Ti). Despite the similarity of the recorded voltammograms the faradaic efficiency (i.e. selectivity towards oxygen evolution) decreases in the studied chloride concentration range from 100% (in pure acid) to ca. 80 % (at 0.3M concentration) [12].

This change in selectivity should reflect also in the operando recorded O K edge spectra (see Figs 7-11). A comparison of the 2D maps reflecting a change in absorbance in 525-535 eV range, however, does not show a pronounced effect of the chloride presence on the recorded spectral response (see Fig. 7). The differential absorption spectra on O K edge are dominated by potential driven change of absorption at 529 eV, 531 eV and 533 eV as one should expect for an oxygen evolution on Ru based oxides [31, 33]. A detailed analysis of the change of the absorption coefficient at individual energies corresponding to OH/O (529 eV), O₂/OOH (531 eV) and to local electron structure resonance (533 eV), however outlines a slight change of the spectral behavior with respect to the RuO₂.

One of the notable changes is observed for the absorption of OH/O surface confined species (see Figure 8b-11b). The absorption signal located at 529 eV shows a reversible increase with increasing potential in the potential range 1.0-1.7 V vs RHE. The accumulation of these oxygen containing species is evident already at potentials significantly negative to the standard potential of oxygen evolution. In this light one cannot attribute this accumulation of the surface oxygen species directly to intermediates of the oxygen evolution process. It also needs to be noted that the spectral signal at 529 eV is affected neither by chloride concentration nor electrode history. Given the fact that the selectivity of the Ru-Mn-O electrode towards oxygen evolution decreases with increasing chloride concentration one may assume that this buildup of oxygen at the electrode surface is not directly related to the anodic gas evolution reactions.

While the 2 D maps do not suggest a profound change of absorption in the region indicative for formation of gaseous oxygen or accumulation of peroxo species at the electrode surface (531 eV) a closer examination reveals a change of the recorded spectral response both with electrolyte concentration as well as with electrode history (see Fig. 8a-11a). In absence of chlorides the absorption signal at 531 eV increases reversibly with potential. In the anodic scan the absorption coefficient remains constant until one reaches a potential of ca. 1.4 V vs RHE which coincides with an onset of the exponential increase of the anodic current. The absorption signal remains practically proportional to the applied potential at all potentials above 1.5 V. A change in the polarization direction leads also to a decrease of the absorption coefficient. A potential controlled decrease of the absorption coefficient in the cathodic scan of each cycle is evident for potentials positive to ca. 1.4 V vs RHE.

The spectra behavior at 531 eV qualitatively changes even after addition of the smallest amount of chlorides. In chloride containing solutions the absorption at 531 eV starts to

increase at rather negative potentials of about 1.0 V vs RHE. This onset of absorption increase at 531 eV appears ca 0.5 V earlier than in absence of chlorides. It needs to be stressed that under these conditions the observed increase in absorption cannot be related to evolved oxygen and represents solely an accumulation of OOH groups at the surface. Surprisingly, the absorption coefficient at 531 eV stops increasing with applied potential at 1.4 V when one observes an onset of the exponential current increase. While on the pristine electrode the absorption coefficient reaches a plateau the subsequent cycling shows a clear decrease of the absorption at 531 eV. It needs to be noted that this qualitative change of the absorption behavior brings up a pronounced hysteresis between anodic and cathodic branches (see Fig. 9a-11a).

The qualitative absorption change at 531 eV which reflects either oxygen evolution or formation and accumulation of the of the OOH species, is reflected in absorption at 533 eV. The absorption behavior at 533 eV reflects gradual development of the catalysts electronic structure under operando conditions. Regardless of the chloride concentration the absorption coefficient at 533 eV decreases with increasing electrode potentials positive to 1.4 V vs RHE. This absorption change coincides with the decrease of the absorption at 533 eV (see Figure 8c-11c).

The behavior observed on Ru-Mn-O electrodes sheds additional light on the OER mechanism on Ru-Mn-O phases. In absence of chlorides the XAS data do not allow to identify the rate limiting step in the oxygen evolution process. The increase of the absorption at 529 eV which is characteristic for an accumulation of OH/O at the surface is observed almost in the entire potential range of the experiment. This does not allow for unambiguous assignment of these species to the OER catalytic cycle since the formation of the species is recorded even at

potentials significantly negative to standard potential of oxygen evolution. A weak connection of the accumulation of the OH/O at surface with the oxygen evolution process is further demonstrated by the fact that the change of the absorption coefficient at 529 eV is practically insensitive to presence of chlorides.

A detailed analysis of the absorption at 531 eV qualifies the selectivity of the ruthenium manganese oxides in parallel oxygen and chlorine evolution. First of all one needs to stress that the accumulation of OOH in presence and absence of chlorides follows a different behavior. In the absence of chlorides the OOH formation and accumulation is not observed before onset of the exponential anodic current and continuous increase of population of all conceivable intermediates of OER with potential does not allow to pin down a single reaction step as a rate limiting one. On the other hand, in presence of chlorides the accumulation of OOH proceeds well before the actual onset of gas evolving reactions. In this case the onset of gaseous oxygen evolution is accompanied by a decrease of the OOH population at the surface. This type of behavior is consistent with a situation in which the third electron transfer becomes rate limiting. The observed behavior then suggests that the addition of chlorides streamlines the oxygen evolution process on Ru-Mn-O surfaces from multiple mechanisms which apparently apply in absence of chlorides to a single one in which the oxygen evolution process is controlled by the third electron transfer. The recorded spectra also suggest that oxygen evolving process is still confined to the vicinity of the surface Ru as attests the decrease of the available energy levels formed by a hybridization of $2p^*$ orbitals with Ru $3d e_g$ orbitals. The overall electrocatalytic activity of Ru-Mn-O catalysts is still characterized by relatively pronounced change of the electronic structure reflecting the transfer of the electrons from water to the electrode through catalyst. The actual effect of the present Mn – which seems to

be essential in steering the selectivity of the Ru-Mn-O surfaces - cannot be elucidated from experimental spectra and would require a dedicated theoretical study.

Conclusions

The in-situ O K edge X-ray absorption spectra adequately reflect the difference both between the state of the oxide electrode in oxygen and in parallel oxygen and chlorine evolution. In the case of RuO₂ the oxygen evolution in absence of chlorides is characterized by an accumulation of surface confined OOH (3rd electron transfer intermediate) and by formation of gaseous oxygen both showing a potential triggered increase of absorption at 531 eV. The oxygen evolution process is further characterized by a change of the local electronic structure which shows a decrease of the absorption at 533 eV. This decrease of the absorption can be related to electrons being removed from the water molecule via interaction with cus sites of the catalyst due to which one observes an anomalous filling of the 3d e_g orbitals during oxygen evolution. The presence of chlorides changes the surface behavior in such a way that the surface of the RuO₂ gets gradually selective for chlorine evolution instead of oxygen evolution. This shows itself in gradual suppression of the absorption increase at 531 eV which is otherwise typical for OER. This suppression is more pronounced in subsequent cycles suggesting that the selective chlorine evolution requires an initial formation of the surface confined OOH species. The shift of the selectivity towards chlorine evolution is further demonstrated by the absorption at 533 eV which, in contrast to the behavior typical for chloride free solution, shows a potential controlled in absorption.

In the case of Ru-Mn-O oxides which retain high selectivity towards oxygen evolution even in presence of chlorides the O K edge spectra clearly show that both competing processes proceed on different fractions of the catalysts surface. In absence of chlorides one observes a

suppression of the formation of surface OOH intermediates at potentials preceding the exponential oxygen evolution. Such a behavior is compliant that none of the conceived reaction steps exerts kinetic control. The oxygen evolution process is again accompanied with a decreasing absorption at 533 eV in the oxygen evolution region confirming the essential interaction of the OER intermediates with the catalysts surface is done primarily via cus sites in a manner similar to the RuO_2 . In presence chloride, on the other hand, one observes a significant accumulation of surface confined OOH also at potential negative to the OER onset. The population of surface confined OOH drops rapidly once the oxygen evolution starts indicating that the OER in presence of chlorides is kinetically controlled by the third electron transfer.

The available spectroscopic data suggest that in the case of the Ru based/dominated materials the key factor affecting the selectivity between chlorine and oxygen evolution is the ability of the catalyst to leave the surface confined cus Ru sites chloride free under reaction conditions. Apparently, this is much easier achieved in the case of Ru-Mn-O materials than of the RuO_2 . The experimental data indicate that chloride absorption in fact promotes a formation of OOH sites on Ru-Mn-O phases. A conclusive answer resolving this situation, however, needs to be based on a dedicated theoretical study.

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References:

- [1] Gong, M.; Dai, H.A. Mini Review of NiFe-Based Materials as Highly Active Oxygen Evolution Reaction Electrocatalysts. *Nano Res.* **2015** *8*, 23–39. DOI: 10.1007/s12274-014-0591-z.
- [2] Tong, W.; Forster, M.; Dionigi, F.; Dresch, S.; Erami, R. S.; Strasser, P.; Cowan, A. J.; Farràs, P. Electrolysis of low-grade and saline surface water. *Nature Energy* **2020**, *5*, 367–377. D.O.I.: [10.1038/s41560-020-0550-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-020-0550-8).
- [3] Balaji, R.; Kannan, B. S.; Lakshmi, J.; Senthil, N.; Vasudevan, S.; Sozhan, G.; Shukla, A. K. ; Ravichandran, S. An alternative approach to selective sea water oxidation for hydrogen production, *Electrochem. Com.*, **2009**, *11*,1700-1702, DOI: 10.1016/j.elecom.2009.06.022.
- [4] Farras, P.; Strasser, P.; Cowan, A.J. Water electrolysis – direct from the sea or not to be?, *Joule*, **2021**, *5* 1921-1923, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2021.07.014>.
- [5] Petrykin, V.; Macounová, K.; Shlyakhtin, O. A.; Krtil, P. Tailoring Selectivity for Electrocatalytic Oxygen Evolution on Ruthenium Oxides by Zn Substitution, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **2010**, *49*, 4813-4815, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.200907128>.
- [6] M. Schalenbach, G. Tjarks, M. Carmo, W. Lueke, M. Mueller, D. Stolten, Acidic or alkaline? Towards a new perspective on the efficiency of water electrolysis, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **163** (2016) F3197–F3208, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0271611jes>.
- [7] Liang, C., Rao, R.R., Svane, K.L. et al. Unravelling the effects of active site density and energetics on the water oxidation activity of iridium oxides. *Nat Catal* **7**, 763–775 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41929-024-01168-7>
- [8] Hansen, H.; Man, I.C.; Studt, F.; Abild-Pedersen, F.; Bligaard, T.; Rossmeisl, J. Electrochemical Chlorine Evolution at Rutile Oxide (110) Surfaces, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, **2010**, *12*, 283-290, DOI: 10.1039/B917459A.

- [9] Abbott, D. F.; Petrykin, V.; Okube, M.; Bastl, Z.; Krtil, P. Selective Chlorine Evolution Catalysts Based on Mg-Doped Nanoparticulate Ruthenium Dioxide, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **2015**, *162*, H23-H31. DOI 10.1149/2.0541501jes
- [10] J. Scholz, M. Risch, G. Wartner, C. Luderer, V. Roddatis, C. Jooss, Tailoring the oxygen evolution activity and stability using defect chemistry, *Catalysts* 7 (2017) 139, <https://doi.org/10.3390/catal7050139>.
- [11] Petrykin, V.; Bastl, Z.; Franc, J.; Macounova, K.; Makarova, M.; Mukerjee, S.; Ramaswamy, N.; Spirovova, I.; Krtil, P. Local Structure of Nanocrystalline Ru_{1-x}Ni_xO_{2-δ} Dioxide and Its Implications for Electrocatalytic Behavior-An XPS and XAS Study, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, **2009**, *113*, 21657-21666, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp904935e>.
- [12] Astudillo, C.; Minhová Macounová, K.; Malthe Frandsen, A.; Nebel, R.; Rossmeisl, J.; Krtil, P. Ru rich Ru-Mn-O phases for selective suppression of chlorine evolution in sea water electrolysis, *Electrochim. Acta*, **2023**, *470*, 143295, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2023.143295>.
- [13] Hao Liu, Wei Shen, Huanyu Jin, Jun Xu, Pinxian Xi, Juncai Dong, Yao Zheng, Shi-Zhang Qiao, High-Performance Alkaline Seawater Electrolysis with Anomalous Chloride Promoted Oxygen Evolution Reaction, *Angewandte Chemie Int. Ed*, **62**(46) (2023) e202311674,
- [14] M. Maril, J.L. Delplancke, N. Cisternas, P. Tobosque, Y. Maril, C. Carrasco, Critical aspects in the development of anodes for use in seawater electrolysis, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 47 (2022) 3532–3549, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2021.11.002>
- [15] S. Dresp, F. Dionigi, S. Loos, J. Ferreira de Araujo, C. Spori, M. Gliech, H. Dau, P. Strasser, Direct electrolytic splitting of seawater: activity, selectivity, degradation, and recovery studied from the molecular catalyst structure to the electrolyzer cell level, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 8 (2018), <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201800338>
- [16] Astudillo, C.; Minhová Macounová, K.; Nebel, R. Plšek, J.; Krtil, P. Selectivity of Mn rich Ru Mn O phases in parallel oxygen and chlorine evolution, *Electrochim. Acta*, **2024**, *492*, 144346, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2024.144346>
- [17] Hammer, B.; Hansen, L.; Nørskov, J. Improved Adsorption Energetics Within Density-Functional Theory Using Revised Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof functionals, *Phys. Rev. B*, **1999**, *59*, 7413, 10.1103/PhysRevB.59.7413.

- [18] Vos, J.G.; Wezendonk, T.A.; Jeremiasse, J.; Koper, M. T. M. MnOx/IrOx as Selective Oxygen Evolution Electrocatalyst in Acidic Chloride Solution, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **2018**, *140* (2018) 10272-10281, doi: 10.1021/jacs.8b05382.
- [19] Exner, K.; Anton, J.; Jacob, T.; Over, H. Controlling Selectivity in the Chlorine Evolution Reaction over RuO₂-Based Catalysts, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **2014**, *53*, 11032-11035, d.o.i.: [10.1002/anie.201406112](https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201406112).
- [20] Man, I.C.; Su, H.-Y.; Calle-Vallejo, F.; Hansen, H.A.; Martínez, J.I.; Inoglu, N.G.; Kitchin, J.; Jaramillo, T.F.; Nørskov, J.K.; Rossmeisl, J; Universality in oxygen evolution electrocatalysis on oxide surfaces, *ChemCatChem*, **2011**,*3*, 1159-1165, d.o.i. [10.1002/cctc.201000397](https://doi.org/10.1002/cctc.201000397).
- [21] R.G. Gonzalez-Huerta, G, P.B.Balbuena Ramos-S´anchez, Oxygen evolution in Co-doped RuO₂ and IrO₂: experimental and theoretical insights to diminish electrolysis overpotential, *J. Power Sources* **268** (2014) 69–76, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2014.06.029>.
- [22] R.K.B. Karlsson, A. Cornell, L.G.M. Pettersson, The electrocatalytic properties of doped TiO₂, *Electrochim. Acta* **180** (2015) 514–527, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2015.08.101>
- [23] Karlsson, R.K.B; Hansen, H.; Bligaard, T.; Cornell, A.; Pettersson, L. G. M. Ti Atoms in Ru_{0.3}Ti_{0.7}O₂ Mixed Oxides Form Active and Selective Sites for Electrochemical Chlorine Evolution, *Electrochim. Acta*, **2014**, *146*, 733-740, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2014.09.056> .
- [24] Karlsson, R.K.B.; Cornell, A.; Pettersson, L.G.M. The Electrocatalytic Properties of Doped TiO₂. *Electrochim. Acta*, **2015**, *180*, 514-527, DOI: [10.1016/j.electacta.2015.08.101](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2015.08.101).
- [25] Malmgren, C.; Hummelgard, M., Backstrom, J.; Cornell, A.; Olin, H. Nanoscale characterization of crystallinity in DSA® coating, *J. Physics Conf. Series*, **2008**, *100*, 052026, doi:10.1088/1742-6596/100/5/052026.
- [26] Adiga, P.; Nunn, W.; Wong, C. ; Manjeshwar, A.K.; Nair, S.; Jalan, B.; Stoerzinger, K.A. Breaking OER and CER scaling relations via strain and its relaxation in RuO₂ (101), *Mat. Today Energy*, **2022**, *28*, 101087, d.o.i:10.1016/j.mtener.2022.101087.

- [27] Minhová Macounová, K.; Pittkowski, R.K.; Nebel, R.; Zitolo, A.; Krtil, P.; Selectivity of Ru-rich Ru-Ti-O oxide surfaces in parallel oxygen and chlorine evolution reactions, *Electrochim. Acta*, **2022**, 420, 140878.
- [28] Vos, J.G.; Liu, Z.; Speck, F.D.; Perini, N.; Fu, W.; Cherevko, S.; Koper, M.T.M. Selectivity Trends Between Oxygen Evolution and Chlorine Evolution on Iridium-Based Double Perovskites in Acidic Media. *ACS Catal.* **2019**, 9 (2), 8561-8574, d.o.i:10.1021/acscatal.9b01159
- [29] Vélez, J.J.V.; Bernsmeier, D.; Jones, T.E.; Zeller, P.; Carbonio, E.; Chuang, C.; Falling, L.J.; Streibel, V.; Mom, R.V.; Hammud, A.; Hävecker, M.; Arrigo, R.; Stotz, E.; Lunkenbein, T.; Knop-Gericke, A.; Krähnert, R.; Schlögl, R. The Rise of Electrochemical NAPXPS Operated in the Soft X-ray Regime Exemplified by the Oxygen Evolution Reaction on IrO_x Electrocatalysts. *Faraday Discussions*. 236 (**2022**), 103–125, DOI: 10.1039/D1FD00114K.
- [30] Amemiya, K.; Sakata, K.; Suzuki-Sakamaki, M. Development of Fluorescence-Yield Wavelength-Dispersive X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy in the Soft X-ray Region for Time-Resolved Experiments. *Rev. Sci. Instrum.*, **2020**, 91, 93104. DOI: 10.1063/5.0021981.
- [31] Deka, N.; Jones, T. E.; Falling, L. J.; Sandoval-Diaz, L.-E.; Lunkenbein, T.; Velasco-Velez, J.-J.; Chan, T.-S.; Chuang, C.-H.; Knop-Gericke, A.; Mom, R. V. On the Operando Structure of Ruthenium Oxides during the Oxygen Evolution Reaction in Acidic Media *ACS Catalysis*, **2023**, 13, 7488-7498, doi:10.1021/acscatal.3c01607
- [32] Sakata, K.; Amemiya, K. Development of Operando Observation Technique of Electrochemical Reactions at the Solid-Liquid Interface by Fluorescence-Yield Wavelength-Dispersive Soft X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy., *Chem. Lett.*, **2021**, 50, 1710. DOI: 10.1246/cl.210380.
- [33] Sakata, K.; Minhova Macounova, K.; Amemiya, K.; Krtil, P. Structural Development on Ru and RuO₂ Electrodes during Oxygen Evolution – an operando soft X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy Approach, *Electrochim. Acta* **2024**, 507, 145066, doi:10.1016/j.electacta.2024.145066.

- [34] Kondoh, H. Surface science study on catalytic surfaces under working conditions with soft-X-ray surface spectroscopy at the Photon Factory. *Surf. Sci.*, (2025), 753, 122657. DOI: [10.1016/j.susc.2024.122657](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susc.2024.122657).
- [35] Amemiya, K.; Toyoshima, A.; Kikuchi, T.; Kosuge, T.; Nigorikawa, K.; Sumii, R.; Ito, K. Commissioning of a Soft X-ray Beamline PF-BL-16A With a Variable-Included-Angle Varied-Line-Spacing Grating Monochromator. *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 2010, 1234, 295–298. DOI: 10.1063/1.3463193.
- [36] Occhialini, C. A.; Bisogni, V.; You, H.; Barbour, A.; Jarrige, I.; Mitchell, J. F.; Comin, R.; Pellicciari, J. Local electronic structure of rutile RuO₂ *Phys. Rev. Res.*, 2021, 3, 033214. Doi:10.1103/PhysRevResearch.3.033214
- [37] Frati, F.; Hunault, M.O.J.Y; de Groot, F.M.F. Oxygen K-edge X-ray Absorption Spectra. *Chem. Rev.* 2020, 120, 4056–4110. DOI: 10.1021/acs.chemrev.9b00439.
- [38] P-A. Bergstrom, J. Lindgren, O. Kristiansson, An IR Study of the Hydration of ClO₄⁻, NO₃⁻, I⁻, Br⁻, Cl⁻ and SO₄²⁻ Anions in Aqueous Solution, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, 95, 8575-8580

Figures

Figure 1 (a) Schematic representation of the apparatus for energy-dispersive XAS on O K-edge and (b) a dedicated electrochemical cell.

(a) Wavelength-dispersive XAS

(b) Electrochemical cell

Figure 2

Figure 2 Cyclic voltammograms recorded on thermally grown RuO_2 electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 (left) and 0.1M HClO_4 containing 0.05 M NaCl (right) at a polarization rate of 5 mV/s.

Figure 3

Figure 3 2D colored surface maps showing the progression of O K-edge spectra of (RuO₂ electrode during cyclic polarization in 0.1 M HClO₄ (top) and in 0.1 M HClO₄ containing 0.05 M NaCl (bottom) at 5 mV/s. The map summarizes the development of the populations of oxygen containing species at the RuO₂ surface during first 3 cycles. The color scheme represents the absorption coefficient as a function of the electrode potential.

Figure 4a

Fig 4a A comparison of the potential dependence of the absorption coefficient $\Delta\mu$ at 531 eV, during cyclic of the thermally grown RuO_2 electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 (left) and in 0.1 M HClO_4 containing 0.05 M NaCl (right) at 5 mV/s. The arrows mark the direction of the polarization.

Figure 4b

Fig. 4b A comparison of the potential dependence of the absorption coefficient $\Delta\mu$ at 529 eV, as a function of the electrode potential during cyclic of the thermally grown RuO_2 electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 (left) and in 0.1 M HClO_4 containing 0.05 M NaCl (right) at 5 mV/s. The arrows mark the direction of the polarization.

Figure 4c

Fig. 4c A comparison of the potential dependence of the absorption coefficient $\Delta\mu$ at 533 eV, as a function of the electrode potential during cyclic of the thermally grown RuO_2 electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 (left) and in 0.1 M HClO_4 containing 0.05 M NaCl (right) at 5 mV/s. The arrows mark the direction of the polarization.

Figure 4d

Fig. 4d A comparison of the potential dependence of the absorption coefficient $\Delta\mu$ at 534 eV, as a function of the electrode potential during cyclic of the thermally grown RuO_2 electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 (left) and in 0.1 M HClO_4 containing 0.05 M NaCl (right) at 5 mV/s. The arrows mark the direction of the polarization.

Figure 5

Fig. 5 O Kedge X-ray absorption spectra of $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ (black) and $\text{Ru}_{0.8}\text{Mn}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$ (red).

Figure 6

Fig. 6 Cyclic voltammograms recorded on spray freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 containing variable content of chloride at a polarization rate of 5 mV/s. The actual chloride concentrations are marked in Figure legend. The vertical lines mark the onset of double layer region (green) and exponential current increase (orange) and were added to guide the eye.

Figure 7

Figure 7a 2D colored surface maps showing the progression of O K-edge spectra of $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode during cyclic polarization in 0.1 M HClO_4 at 5 mV/s. The map summarizes the development of the populations of oxygen containing species at the surface during first 3 cycles. The color scheme represents the absorption coefficient as a function of the electrode potential.

Figure 7b 2D colored surface maps showing the progression of O K-edge spectra of ($\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$) electrode during cyclic polarization in 0.1 M HClO_4 /0.01 M NaCl at 5 mV/s. The map summarizes the development of the populations of oxygen containing species at the surface during first 3 cycles. The color scheme represents the absorption coefficient as a function of the electrode potential.

Figure 7c 2D colored surface maps showing the progression of O K-edge spectra of $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode during cyclic polarization in 0.1 M HClO_4 /0.05 M NaCl at 5 mV/s. The map summarizes the development of the populations of oxygen containing species at the surface during first 3 cycles. The color scheme represents the absorption coefficient as a function of the electrode potential.

Figure 7d 2D colored surface maps showing the progression of O K-edge spectra of $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode during cyclic polarization in 0.1 M HClO_4 /0.01 M NaCl at 5 mV/s. The map summarizes the development of the populations of oxygen containing species at the surface during first 3 cycles. The color scheme represents the absorption coefficient as a function of the electrode potential.

Figure 8a Potential dependence reflecting a variation of absorption coefficient change at $\Delta\mu$ at 531 eV during cyclic of the spray freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 at 5 mV/s.

Figure 8b Potential dependence reflecting a variation of absorption coefficient change at $\Delta\mu$ at 529 eV during cyclic of the spray freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 at 5 mV/s.

Figure 8c Potential dependence reflecting a variation of absorption coefficient change at $\Delta\mu$ at 533 eV (bottom) during cyclic of the spray freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 at 5 mV/s.

Fig 9a Potential dependence reflecting a variation of absorption coefficient change at $\Delta\mu$ at 531 eV during cyclic polarization of the spray freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 containing 0.01 M of NaCl at 5 mV/s.

Fig 9b Potential dependence reflecting a variation of absorption coefficient change at $\Delta\mu$ at 529 eV during cyclic polarization of the spray freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 containing 0.01 M of NaCl at 5 mV/s.

Fig 9 Potential dependence reflecting a variation of absorption coefficient change at $\Delta\mu$ at 533 eV (bottom) during cyclic polarization of the spray freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 containing 0.01 M of NaCl at 5 mV/s.

Fig. 10a Potential dependence reflecting a variation of absorption coefficient change at $\Delta\mu$ at 531 eV during cyclic polarization of the spray freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 containing 0.05 M of NaCl at 5 mV/s.

Fig. 10b Potential dependence reflecting a variation of absorption coefficient change at $\Delta\mu$ at 529 eV during cyclic polarization of the spray freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 containing 0.05 M of NaCl at 5 mV/s.

Fig. 10c Potential dependence reflecting a variation of absorption coefficient change at $\Delta\mu$ at 533 eV during cyclic polarization of the spray freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 containing 0.05 M of NaCl at 5 mV/s.

Fig. 11a Potential dependence reflecting a variation of absorption coefficient change at $\Delta\mu$ at 531 eV during cyclic polarization of the spray freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 containing 0.10 M of NaCl at 5 mV/s.

Fig. 11b Potential dependence reflecting a variation of absorption coefficient change at $\Delta\mu$ at 529 eV during cyclic polarization of the spray freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 containing 0.10 M of NaCl at 5 mV/s.

Fig. 10c Potential dependence reflecting a variation of absorption coefficient change at $\Delta\mu$ at 533 eV (bottom) during cyclic polarization of the spray freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 containing 0.05 M of NaCl at 5 mV/s.

TOC

